

Leximancer Software for Qualitative Data Analysis: A Follow-up on the ‘Voices from the University Classrooms’ Report

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Abstract

The current paper discusses the modern days’ affordances of the digital tools in service of the educational qualitative research. In the focus of this report is the follow-up project on the previously presented study, which was concerned with the international polylingual English as an Additional Language (EAL) students’ perspectives on teaching and learning with the means of multimodality. This qualitative case study, approved by the IRB committee and rested on the socio-cultural theory was conducted with 12 International students in the North-Eastern USA.

The research question was concerned with the affect from the multimodal means of education on the readers’ ability to understand the dense-content texts. The research found that all the subjects largely and predominantly relied on the available modes of multimodality. In contrast to the antecedent talk, which delineated the entire study, its theoretical considerations, design, method, and findings, this proposed demonstration aims to solely introduce the audiences to the advantages of the usage of the Leximancer software serving the needs of the educational research. The major purpose of this exhibition is to acquaint the audiences with the modern days’ research instruments offered by digitality. Following a brief introduction to the general highlights of the preceding presentation of the discussed study, the author will center the attention on the processes and outcomes of working with the Leximancer software for analyzing the voices of the research subjects in the form of their transcribed interviews. The benefit to the audiences from this presentation is in their getting familiarized with the new methods and techniques in processing the extensive data from the qualitative research in faster and significantly more efficient digital ways.

Keywords: Digitality, follow-up project, Leximancer, software, qualitative research tools